

Demographics

Record ID

Participant Name

Date of birth

Sex

Male Female

NHS number

GP Name/Practice

Ethnicity

- White - British
- White - Irish
- White - any other White background
- Mixed - White and Black Caribbean
- Mixed - White and Black African
- Mixed - White and Asian
- Mixed - any other mixed background
- Asian or Asian British - Indian
- Asian or Asian British - Pakistani
- Asian or Asian British - Bangladeshi
- Asian or Asian British - any other Asian background
- Black or Black British - Caribbean
- Black or Black British - African
- Black or Black British - any other Black background
- Other ethnic groups - Chinese
- Other ethnic group - Any other ethnic group
- Not stated
- Not known

Last domiciliary postcode

What is your highest level of educational qualification?

- Degree level or Degree equivalent or above (for example first or higher degrees, postgraduate diplomas, NVQ/SVQ level 4 or 5, etc)
- Qualifications below degree level (for example an A-level, SCE Higher, GCSE, O-level, SCE Standard/Ordinary, NVQ/SVQ, BTEC, etc)
- No qualifications
- Do not know or cannot remember
- Prefer not to say
- Not applicable

Form completed by:

((initials))

Consent info and CONSULT

Date of approach

(screening date)

Bed space / room number

Does the participant have capacity to consent?

- Yes
 No
(if yes, continue to consent; if no, seek consultee)

Participant contact number:

(Please provide contact phone number or email)

Participant email:

Has consultee been identified?

- Yes
 No

Name of consultee

Consultee contact number

Consultee email

Allocated CONSULT ID?

- Yes
 No

CONSULT ID number:

(Please complete CONSULT log)

Randomised to:

- decision aide
 information only

Has TRACS consent been obtained?

- Yes
 No

Is consent recorded on:

- Paper form
 REDCap

Form completed by:

(initials)

Participant Consent form

I confirm that I have read and understood the Patient Information Sheet (version 1.0 dated 28 Sep 2022) for the TRACS Liverpool Study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

- Yes
 No

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw my consent at any time, without giving any reason, without my normal medical care or legal rights being affected. I understand that I can agree to take part in different aspects of the study and will indicate my choice below.

- Yes
 No

I understand that relevant information about me will be collected from my medical records and other health and social care-related records and looked at by the research team and responsible practitioners during the study. This information may also be reviewed by regulatory bodies and NHS Trusts where it is relevant to conduct of this study. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records and for my GP to be contacted.

- Yes
 No

I understand that any information collected about me (including name and address) will be held at the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine according to the 2018 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679). I understand that this information will be kept securely, and viewed and shared with the TRACS Liverpool research team and other approved organisations in accordance with my choices below. I understand that no personal identifiable information will be used in the study report or publications. Identifiable data will be kept for up to 12 months after which it will be destroyed.

- Yes
 No

I agree to take part in the study.

- Yes
 No

Please select which aspects you agree to take part in:

I agree that information from me and my records can be collected for the duration of the study.

- Yes
 No

I agree that stool samples or rectal swabs can be collected, tested and stored during the current active sampling periods on my inpatient ward or care homes.

- Yes
 No

I agree that stool samples or rectal swabs can be collected, tested and stored during future active sampling periods on my inpatient ward or care home if I remain an inpatient or resident.

- Yes
 No

I agree to join the optional enhanced sampling group which will collect, send, test and store stool samples or rectal swabs between active sampling periods for the duration of the study.

- Yes
- No

I agree that relevant health and social care data about me which is held by other health, government or research organisations such as NHS Digital or CIPHA can be shared with TRACS Liverpool where appropriate approvals are in place. I understand that this will include data covering the year prior to my enrolment in TRACS Liverpool and for the duration of TRACS-Liverpool. In order for this to occur personal identifiers (such as my NHS number) will need to be shared securely with these organisations.

- Yes
- No

I agree that anonymised information collected as part of this study and stool samples and rectal swabs stored can be used in other research studies (including with other researchers) which have been approved by appropriate NHS (or equivalent) regulatory bodies.

- Yes
- No

I agree to be contacted in future by researchers who may want to interview me about my health experiences, my views on antimicrobial resistance, and what it was like to take part in the TRACS Liverpool study. I understand that they will take a further consent for enrolment in this and any future study.

- Yes
- No

Please sign or initial below to confirm your consent to taking part in the study

Full name

Date

Researcher name:

TRACS 2 Consent version 2.0 14th December 2022

Consultee form

I confirm that I have been consulted about my relative/friend's participation in this research project. I have read and understood the Consultee Information Sheet (version 2.0 dated 14 Dec 2022) for the TRACS Liverpool Study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

- Yes
 No

Name of potential participant (friend/relative):

I understand that I can request he/she is withdrawn from the study at any time, without giving any reason, and without his/her normal care or legal rights being affected. I understand that I can agree for him/her to take part in different aspects of the study and will indicate my choice below.

- Yes
 No

I understand that relevant information about him/her will be collected from his/her medical records and other health and social care-related records and looked at by the research team and responsible practitioners during the study. I understand that their GP may be contacted to facilitate this. This information may also be reviewed by regulatory bodies and NHS Trusts where it is relevant to conduct of this study.

- Yes
 No

I understand that any information collected about my friend/relative (including name and address) will be held at the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine according to the 2018 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679). I understand that this information will be kept securely, and viewed and shared with the TRACS Liverpool research team and other approved organisations in accordance with my choices below. I understand that no personal identifiable information will be used in the study report or publications. Identifiable data will be kept for up to 12 months after which it will be destroyed.

- Yes
 No

In my opinion my friend/relative would have no objection to taking part in this study.

- Yes
 No

Please select which aspects you agree to take part in:

I understand that information from my friend/relative and his/her records can be collected for the duration of the study.

- Yes
 No

I understand that stool samples or rectal swabs will be collected, tested and stored during the current active sampling periods on my friend/relative's inpatient ward or care homes.

- Yes
 No

I agree that stool samples or rectal swabs can be collected, tested and stored during future active sampling periods on my friend/relative's inpatient ward or care home if they remain an inpatient or resident.

- Yes
- No

In my opinion my friend/relative would have no objection to joining the optional enhanced sampling group which will collect, send, test and store stool samples or rectal swabs between active sampling periods for the duration of the study.

- Yes
- No

I understand that relevant health and social care data about my friend/relative which is held by other health, government or research organisations such as NHS Digital or CIPHA can be shared with TRACS Liverpool where appropriate approvals are in place. I understand that this will include data covering the year prior to enrolment in TRACS Liverpool and for the duration of TRACS-Liverpool. In order for this to occur personal identifiers (such as NHS number) will need to be shared securely with these organisations.

- Yes
- No

I understand that anonymised information collected as part of this study and stool samples and rectal swabs stored can be used in other research studies (including with other researchers) which have been approved by appropriate NHS (or equivalent) regulatory bodies.

- Yes
- No

Please sign or initial below to confirm your agreement to your friend/relative taking part in the study

Full name of consultee

Date

Relationship to participant:

Researcher name:

TRACS 2 Consultee declaration version 2.0 14th December 2022

Care Dependency Score

Date _____

Eating and drinking
The extent to which the patient is able to satisfy his/her need for food and drink

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Continence
The extent to which the patient is able to control the discharge of urine and faeces voluntarily

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Body posture
The extent to which the patient is able to adopt a position appropriate to a certain activity

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Mobility
The extent to which the patient is able to move about unaided

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Day/night pattern
The extent to which the patient can maintain an appropriate day/night cycle unaided

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Getting dressed and undressed
The extent to which the patient is able to get dressed and undressed unaided

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Body temperature The extent to which the patient is able to protect his/her body temperature against external influences unaided	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others
Hygiene The extent to which the patient is able to take care of his/her personal hygiene unaided	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others
Avoidance of danger The extent to which the patient is able to assure his/her own safety unaided	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others
Communication The extent to which the patient is able to communicate	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others
Contact with others The extent to which the patient is able to appropriately make, maintain and end social contacts	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others
Sense of rules and values The extent to which the patient is able to observe rules by him/herself	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others
Daily activities The extent to which the patient is able to structure daily activities within the facility unaided	<input type="radio"/> Patient is completely dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is partially dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others <input type="radio"/> Patient is almost independent on care from others

Recreational activities
The extent to which the patient is able to participate in activities outside the facility unaided

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Learning ability
The extent to which the patient is able to acquire knowledge and/or skills and/or to retain that which was previously learned unaided

- Patient is completely dependent on care from others
- Patient is to a great extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is partially dependent on care from others
- Patient is only to a limited extent dependent on care from others
- Patient is almost independent on care from others

Form completed by:

((initials))

Clinical Frailty Scale

Date _____

In your clinical setting, after interviewing the subject, please assign them a score of 1 to 7 on the Clinical Frailty Scale:

1 Very Fit - People who are robust, active, energetic and motivated. These people commonly exercise regularly. They are among the fittest for their age.

2 Well - People who have no active disease symptoms but are less fit than category 1. Often, they exercise or are very active occasionally, e.g. seasonally.

3 Managing Well - People whose medical problems are well controlled, but are not regularly active beyond routine walking.

4 Vulnerable - While not dependent on others for daily help, often symptoms limit activities. A common complaint is being "slowed up", and/or being tired during the day.

5 Mildly Frail - These people often have more evident slowing, and need help in high order IADLs (finances, transportation, heavy housework, medications). Typically, mild frailty progressively impairs shopping and walking outside alone, meal preparation and housework.

6 Moderately Frail - People need help with all outside activities and with keeping house. Inside, they often have problems with stairs and need help with bathing and might need minimal assistance (cuing, standby) with dressing.

7 Severely Frail - Completely dependent for personal care, from whatever cause (physical or cognitive). Even so, they seem stable and not at high risk of dying (within ~ 6 months).

8 Very Severely Frail - Completely dependent, approaching the end of life. Typically, they could not recover even from a minor illness.

9. Terminally Ill - Approaching the end of life. This category applies to people with a life expectancy < 6 months, who are not otherwise evidently frail.

Scoring frailty in people with dementia

The degree of frailty corresponds to the degree of dementia. Common symptoms in mild dementia include forgetting the details of a recent event, though still remembering the event itself, repeating the same question/story and social withdrawal.

In moderate dementia, recent memory is very impaired, even though they seemingly can remember their past life events well. They can do personal care with prompting.

In severe dementia, they cannot do personal care without help.

* 1. Canadian Study on Health & Aging, Revised 2008.

2. K. Rockwood et al. A global clinical measure of fitness and frailty in elderly people. CMAJ 2005;173:489-495.

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Form completed by:

((initials))

Antibiotic exposure

Use a separate instance of this form for each Antibiotic

Name of antibiotic

- Amoxicillin
- Azithromycin
- Aztreonam
- Cefalexin
- Ceftazidime
- Ceftriaxone
- Cefuroxime
- Chloramphenicol
- Ciprofloxacin
- Clarithromycin
- Clindamycin
- Co-amoxiclav
- Co-trimoxazole
- Doxycycline
- Erythromycin
- Fidaxomycin
- Flucloxacillin
- Fosfomycin
- Gentamicin
- Levofloxacin
- Linezolid
- Meropenem
- Metronidazole
- Moxifloxacin
- Nitrofurantoin
- Ofloxacin
- Penicillin
- Piperacillin/tazobactam
- Pivmecillinam
- Teicoplanin
- Temocillin
- Tigecycline
- Trimethoprim
- Vancomycin
- Other
(if 'other' please specify)

Other - please specify:

Start date

End date (actual or anticipated)

Route of administration

- Oral
- IV

Dose

Frequency

- Once per day (OD)
- Twice per day (BD)
- Three times per day (TDS)
- Four times per day (QDS)

Week A

Date _____

Location Ward 29 Aintree
 Ward 17B
 Ward 30 Aintree
 Longmoor House
 Estuary House
 Care Home 2
 Care Home 3

Bed space/room number: _____

Date of admission _____

Admitted from: Home
 Care Home
 Hospital
 Intermediate care/rehab
 Other

Please specify: _____

Date of admission to previous location (if known): _____

Currently receiving antibiotics? Yes
 No
(If yes complete abx page)

Antibiotics received in past 3 months? Yes
 No
(If yes complete abx page)

Currently receiving proton pump inhibitors? (eg. lansoprazole, omeprazole) Yes
 No
(If yes please specify)

Name of PPI: Lansoprazole
 Omeprazole
 Esomeprazole
 Other
(If other please specify)

Other - please specify: _____

Any hospital admissions in past 3 months? Yes
 No

If yes please specify:

Any catheters/IV lines/feeding tubes?

- Urinary catheter
 - Nasogastric tube
 - PEG/PEJ (percutaneous feeding tube)
 - Long term indwelling vascular device (PICC/midline/portocath)
 - Short term IV device (peripheral cannula)
 - Other
 - None
(please specify if other)
-

If 'other' please specify:

Any animal exposure in past 3 months? (eg pets, therapy dogs)

- Yes
 - No
-

If yes please specify:

Any overseas travel in past 3 months?

- Yes
 - No
-

If yes please specify:

Clinical Frailty Score completed?

- Yes
 - No
(please complete once for visit A & B)
-

Care Dependency Score completed?

- Yes
 - No
(Please complete once for visit A & B)
-

Sample A1 collected?

- Yes
 - No
(If yes complete sample page)
-

Sample A2 collected?

- Yes
 - No
(If yes complete sample form)
-

Sample A3 collected?

- Yes
 - No
(If yes complete sample page)
-

Week B

Date

Bed space/room number:

Any change to antibiotic treatment?

- Yes
 - No
- (If yes please complete abx page)

Sample B4 collected?

- Yes
 - No
- (If yes complete sample page)

Sample B5 collected?

- Yes
 - No
- (If yes complete sample page)

Sample collection

Type of sample

- rectal swab
- stool sample
- stoma sample

Date sample collected

Bed space/room number:

Sample number

(scan QR code on sample sticker)

Form completed by:

((initials))

Withdrawal

Date of withdrawal

Reason for withdrawal

- Withdrawal of consent (participant)
- Withdrawal of consent (consultee)
- No longer eligible to participate (deterioration in condition)
- Discharged or lost to follow up
- Died

Form completed by:

((initials))

Gp Letter

Date

GP Letter sent

- Yes
- No

Sent by

- Letter
- Email

Initials
